

Recommendations on Digital Publishing in the International Corpus Vitrearum

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Introduction

Context. When the CORPUS VITREARUM MEDII AEVI (CVMA) was founded during the International Congress for the History of Art in Amsterdam in 1952, it brought together various individual initiatives engaged in systematic research into stained glass. The background was devastating: the war had led to the loss and displacement of important stained glass all over Europe. At the same time, extensive photographic campaigns were undertaken in relation to rescued medieval glazing that came to constitute important archives on which systematic publication of stained glass at an international level could be based. The first edition of the guidelines setting out the principles for the CVMA's print publications was composed in 1957. Researchers across Europe, and even across the world, were now able to explore and document European stained glass using common guidelines and to produce comparable and interoperable results for the scientific community and the public. These guidelines have since then been extended to cover stained glass of all centuries (cf. Comité International d'Histoire de l'Art and Union Académique Internationale) and remain the backbone of rather more than one hundred print publications, with more to come – substantial volumes containing comprehensive art-historical knowledge on windows and glass of individual cities or regions.

Today, we need to bring together a diverse range of individual initiatives engaged in systematic stained-glass research. Many research projects and GLAM institutions (Galleries,

¹ This document is written on behalf of the Unit for Digital Resources of the Corpus Vitrearum. The authors would like to thank all members for their valuable contributions.

Libraries, Archives, Museums) are gathering information, digitizing photographs and objects, and providing valuable digital resources on stained glass. The international Corpus Vitrearum (CV) finds itself at a historical juncture: while its guidelines are largely focused on print publications, funders increasingly require hybrid or digital-only publication, even though their exact form is still in flux. Various individual CV initiatives are engaged in finding suitable ways to publish research outcomes in the digital sphere, with solutions tailored to the needs of specific projects. In this situation, the challenge is once again to find common ground within the Corpus Vitrearum and an answer to the question: how do we publish digitally in the CV?

To approach the question, this paper examines the various national contexts, assesses the current situation, and proposes recommendations for digital publication based on standards currently applicable to online publications in the field of art history (cf. Effinger and Kohle, Vaughan). It aims to collate knowledge and experience already gained and make it available to national committees and comparable organizations – not least to build a solid foundation for any digital-publication guidelines that the CV may draw up in future once the dust has settled on the plethora of digital publication formats outlined in this document.

The term ‘publication’. This paper uses a broad definition of ‘publication’ that includes, but is not limited to, making research data (such as images and other media) available; publishing synthesized research (such as essay-style content); and offering digital experiences (such as interactive visualizations). While this definition may not fully align with the CV print guidelines² or those adopted by national research frameworks, it does take into account the general trend in digital publishing towards convergence, a trend that weaves traditionally divided realms like supposedly unpolished data with polished, ‘publication-ready’ results through hypertext linking. As print publishing itself has undergone a digital transformation, these recommendations may also provide orientation within the current, more complex print-publication landscape.

Methodology. The recommendations below are the product of a series of monthly meetings of the Unit for Digital Resources of the Corpus Vitrearum (Digital Unit, DU). The group initially pooled its knowledge on digital publishing and compared both historical and current examples across national committees, as well as across the wider GLAM sector. A second phase consisted of discussions of specific topics and efforts to record observations made in the initial phase. In a third phase, the DU defined the characteristics of different publishing formats and formulated general recommendations. In a final revision phase, the resulting paper was checked against and expanded using relevant literature and legal frameworks.³

General recommendations

- **Peer review:** implement an appropriate form of peer review and ensure transparency about the process for users. The former may range from double-blind peer review to

² The print guidelines specifically mention full catalogues, summary catalogues, and studies as the CV’s main publication formats. Due to the current breadth of digital publication formats, however, this document also takes into account image and metadata publications as well as hybrid formats.

³ The authors expressly encourage further scholarship on the digital dimension of the CV as well as community-centred software development and data stewardship.

expert review by a qualified colleague. The objective is to ensure the scholarly quality of content published under the aegis of the Corpus Vitrearum. In community-oriented projects led by the Corpus Vitrearum, where contributions such as corrections, annotations or addenda are supplied by users, expert moderation and clear content attribution are strongly recommended.

- **Reproduction rights:** ensure that you have full clarity regarding the rights associated with texts, images, and other media intended for publication. Restrictions on the online publication of high-quality images, for example, may influence the choice of platform or even the publication format for a given collection. Additionally, legal frameworks vary across countries. Some countries (such as Germany) provide generous citation rights in academic print publication that may not apply with open-access online publications.
- **Open access:** provide clear re-use licences that are as liberal as possible. This reduces administrative work for the publishing organization, signals reusability to users, and allows copies of content to exist across the web in cases where a service is discontinued.⁴ Creative Commons (CC)⁵ licences provide a widely recognised legal framework. Where re-use licensing is not possible, Rights Statements⁶ can help users to understand permitted and restricted uses.
- **Persistent identifiers:** use some form of persistent identifiers in digital publications wherever possible. As links that an organisation commits to maintaining over time, permalinks offer a basic level of persistence. Alternatively, persistent resource identifiers, such as Document Object Identifiers (DOIs), Archival Resource Keys (ARKs), or other Uniform Resource Names (URNs) may be registered with third-party providers or maintained through institutional services. In such cases, content location changes must be registered with the identifier provider.⁷
- **Citability:** digital collaboration and publishing allows for more complex authorship scenarios than those encountered in early CVMA print volumes. To ensure citability of individual elements, provide clear attributions for texts, images, and other media. This includes identifying user contributions and generated content as such. As with print editions, indicate the version number of any digital content.⁸
- **User workflows:** try to enable scholars and other users to integrate your content into their research workflows. This may include offering download options for images and other media (where reproduction rights permit it), or providing PDF/print layouts for longer texts. Where possible, include machine-readable metadata describing the publication. This enables tools such as citation managers like Zotero⁹ to produce bibliographical citations automatically.

⁴ The European Union, for example, mandates open-access publication since at least 2012 (cf. European Commission).

⁵ <https://creativecommons.org>.

⁶ <https://rightsstatements.org>.

⁷ While third-party services like DOIs are widely adopted, they may still become single points of failure for your publication if they are unavailable. To avoid this, make sure users also have alternative ways of finding your content (such as bibliographies and search engines).

⁸ Some publication systems include version control systems that allow for each published version to be kept available. While this improves reproducibility, it may also come with increased cost and environmental impact.

⁹ <https://www.zotero.org>.

- **Accessibility:** ensure that publications are accessible for users with sensory impairments as well as users who rely on keyboard navigation. This is particularly important for web interfaces and PDFs, as their optional accessibility is a major feature over print-only formats. Avoid overly restrictive rights-management solutions that limit users' ability to copy or process content, as this may unintentionally restrict accessibility, analysis, annotation or citation.¹⁰
- **Communication strategy:** provide users with clear ways to report issues with your publication or provide feedback. A simple and low-cost solution is to provide an email address, for example, in a legal disclaimer. More visible contact details or full-blown user-contributed annotation options are useful tools, but must be carefully designed to encourage constructive contributions while limiting abuse and minimizing moderation efforts.
- **Long-term archival strategy:** ensure you implement a strategy for the long-term availability of your digital publication. Just as physical books degrade over time, data formats and software may become obsolete or unsupported. Hence it is advisable to deposit digital publications with a separate long-term archive if the original publication platform cannot guarantee long-term availability. A typical long-term promise for digital publications currently amounts to a minimum of 10 years.
- **Existing infrastructure:** if possible, use existing research infrastructures rather than platforms maintained only for the duration of a project. Many university libraries, for example, provide publication platforms that automatically syndicate metadata with other catalogues and specialized bibliographies. When publication platforms are purpose-built, base them on well-maintained open-source ecosystems.

Characteristics of digital-publishing formats

Decision aid. The following matrix is designed to offer comparison charts for various digital-publishing formats. Each characteristic features a three-part scale on which a given format (e.g., a catalogue with rich annotations) falls, even if its specific realisation (e.g., Vitrosearch) may differ slightly. Characteristics and scales are presented in a neutral tone to avoid normative judgement. We encourage committees and other interested parties to use this matrix as a decision support tool when selecting publication formats appropriate to their research objectives, community needs, funding environments, and evaluation frameworks.

Audience	General public	Domain-specific	Experts
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Publications typically address specific audiences through language register, content selection, and navigational structure. While 'experts' may include specialists working directly on stained glass, the 'domain-specific' category may also include art historians, conservation professionals, and students. Appealing to the 'general public', on the other hand, means to cater also for amateur communities, school audiences, and non-specialist visitors.

Tradition	Hypertext	Hybrid	Print(-like)
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¹⁰ Visually impaired users, for example, may rely on screen readers that stop functioning when digital rights/restriction management (DRM) is used.

Traditional publishing formats, such as journal articles, essays, or whole volumes, fall into the ‘print(-like)’ category. They are structured sequentially, include relatively few illustrations due to the printing constraints, and rely on support tools such as indexes. These formats are easily reproduced as PDFs. ‘Hypertext’, on the other hand, refers to information systems that are characterized by drill-downs from surface-level information all the way to expert knowledge via links and search functionalities. ‘Hybrid’ publishing models commonly use links to connect information, but also emphasize established document structures.

Research data	Repository	Included/linked	None
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Publishing formats differ greatly in whether they provide synthesized research, the underlying research data, or both. A traditional journal article or essay focuses on presenting new arguments and may, as supporting evidence, include occasional images. It does not, however, commonly feature the original research data beyond references listed in the works cited (‘none’). In a more recent trend towards reproducibility, and enabled by digital formats, some text publications either include or directly link to the images, 3D models, historical records, and other materials used in their production (‘included/linked’). ‘Repository’, by contrast, refers to publications primarily designed to provide research data, even though this may include text treated as one data type among others.

Searchability	Text and media	Mostly images	Mostly text
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Text-based publications are easy to search through various interfaces, such as PDF viewers. However, any images or other media they contain are largely invisible to such tools, except through accompanying descriptions (‘mostly text’). When research data, such as images of stained glass, are published in online catalogues, they are usually annotated with metadata that enables search via specialized interfaces (‘mostly images’). The technically most advanced publication formats allow users to search across both types of content (‘text and media’).

Interoperability	Open standard	Proprietary standard	Platform-specific
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Publication formats differ significantly in their interoperability, depending on how well-established they are: common digital-publishing formats tend to migrate more easily from one platform to another if necessary. ‘Open standard’ refers to publications that use free (as in *libre*) formats established by a standardization body. This includes, for example, IIIF.¹¹ ‘Proprietary standards’ are also common, but there may be costs associated with their use or implementation. This applies, among others, to PDF, for which Adobe Systems holds several patents, even though these are currently licensed royalty-free. The category ‘platform-specific’ includes newer publishing formats that are not (or not yet) standardized. This may lead to additional costs if a given implementation becomes unusable or unsupported.

¹¹ IIIF stands for International Image Interoperability Framework. The standard enables deep zooming into scanned images and pages, and has become the go-to solution for retrodigitisation efforts where the original printed layout is to be preserved.

Funding	Public	Independent	Commercial
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Funding can broadly be categorized as ‘public’, ‘independent’, or ‘commercial’. This characteristic is most meaningful when applied to a specific provider, since most publishing formats are available from various types of providers. Some formats, however, as in the case of social media, specifically imply commercial interest.

Availability	Long-term storage	Project length	Ephemeral content
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Publication formats differ in how long they are typically accessible. Some are commonly stored in institutional repositories (‘long-term storage’). Others depend on project-specific funding and therefore require a long-term archiving strategy once the project concludes (‘project length’). Daily, weekly, or monthly content outside academic journals may theoretically remain accessible for extended periods, but may gradually become difficult or even impossible to locate after a while (‘ephemeral content’).

Curation	Citizen scientists	QA-checked content	Expert authors
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Digital publishing further enables various kinds of content curation beyond the traditional scholar-only model (‘expert authors’). One alternative sees, for example, annotations provided by users included in a digital publication, and such a path may support community-engagement goals. However, implementing proper attribution and expert moderation (‘QA-checked content’) can generate significant overheads. A third model relies primarily on amateur contributors (‘citizen scientists’), though expert review should still be implemented if content is published under the aegis of the Corpus Vitrearum.

Formats for publishing research data

Social Media. Social-media platforms such as Flickr, Instagram, YouTube, or TikTok offer opportunities to include image and video content within feeds that audiences already consume regularly. Publishing research data in this way is comparatively easy and inexpensive for providers, as platforms supply the technical infrastructure in exchange for content that can be monetized. In the effort to keep providers and users on the platform, image and video-editing tools are often included, even if they may not adhere to academic standards of authenticity. Social-media platforms promise to attract interested audiences and facilitate user interaction, even though content is generally more ephemeral than in other publishing environments.

Challenges. The subsidy-in-exchange-for-dependency model means that published data remains subject to the platform provider’s policies and commercial interests. This affects long-term availability, with interfaces geared toward consumption rather than research, opaque advertising practices, automatic licensing for commercial use, unilateral content changes, and the potential reuse of uploaded material as training data for content generators. Such conditions may lead to legal issues arising from conflicting content licences or may violate national requirements regarding digital sovereignty and user privacy,

since the largest social-media companies currently operate under U.S. or Chinese jurisdiction.¹²

Examples. [Archivo audiovisual y oral del Centro Latinoamericano del Vitral, “Stained Glass Windows” group on Flickr](#)

<i>Audience</i>	Broad public	Domain-specific	Experts
<i>Tradition</i>	Hypertext	Hybrid	Print(-like)
<i>Research data</i>	Repository	Included/linked	None
<i>Searchability</i>	Text and media	Mostly images	Mostly text
<i>Interoperability</i>	Open standard	Proprietary standard	Platform-specific
<i>Funding</i>	Public	Independent	Commercial
<i>Availability</i>	Long-term storage	Project length	Ephemeral content
<i>Curation</i>	Citizen scientists	QA-checked content	Expert authors

Catalogues. Digital-image and object catalogues have become one of the most common forms of digital publications within the Corpus Vitrearum. Beyond individual images or objects, catalogues often include structured lists of places, people, organizations (e.g., workshops, owners, commissioners), and occasionally events. A key advantage of this format is the ability to flexibly connect such ‘entities’ within the catalogue. Providers who incorporate persistent identifiers from established authority files significantly increase interoperability and the likelihood that their data can be used in connection to other repositories. Numerous cultural-heritage catalogue solutions are available, whether for self-hosting or through regional, national, or transnational infrastructures.¹³

Challenges. Web-based catalogues are widely accepted within the Corpus Vitrearum community. Compared to printed catalogues, they offer improved navigability, avoid imposing a fixed sequence of entries, and facilitate the reuse of high-quality images in other research contexts. However, other publications can reliably link to catalogue entries only if identifiers remain stable over time. While digital catalogues can, in principle, be continuously updated, maintenance practices vary considerably between providers and projects.

Examples. [Image archive of the German Corpus Vitrearum, BaLAT KIK-IRPA, E-Chastel](#)

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<i>Research data</i>	Repository	Included/linked	None
<i>Searchability</i>	Text and media	Mostly images	Mostly text
<i>Interoperability</i>	Open standard	Proprietary standard	Platform-specific

¹² One way to alleviate these issues is the ‘+1’ strategy where any content made available on a commercial platform needs to be available in a non-commercial context as well.

¹³ Cf. Steller *et al.*

<i>Funding</i>	Public	Independent	Commercial
<i>Availability</i>	Long-term storage	Project length	Ephemeral content
<i>Curation</i>	Citizen scientists	QA-checked content	Expert authors

Catalogues with expert annotations. Catalogues differ in the extent and depth of their annotations. Some projects enrich object records with detailed descriptions, restoration histories, references to iconographic programmes, and bibliographic documentation. This may go so far as to include essay-style texts covering entire buildings, structured by individual windows and supplemented by additional visualizations.

Challenges. This catalogue variant combines structured data, media, and text into a hybrid publication format. Within highly formalized research-evaluation frameworks, the distinction between research data and synthesized research may become blurred, much as in printed Corpus Vitrearum volumes. Furthermore, designing a navigation system that accommodates both linear reading and explorative browsing remains a challenge inherent to the medium.

Examples. [Vitrosearch](#), [Stained Glass in Context](#), [Stained Glass in Wales](#), [From the Ecrin to the Screen](#)

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<i>Tradition</i>	Hypertext	Hybrid	Print(-like)
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<i>Interoperability</i>	Open standard	Proprietary standard	Platform-specific
<i>Funding</i>	Public	Independent	Commercial
<i>Availability</i>	Long-term storage	Project length	Ephemeral content
<i>Curation</i>	Citizen scientists	QA-checked content	Expert authors

Catalogues with wiki-like annotations. With clearly defined editorial guidelines and expert oversight, catalogues may incorporate user contributions. Ideally, citizen scientists can identify and correct errors, enrich authority data, or add contextual information that benefits both scholars and other users. Wiki-based systems (such as Mediawiki and Wikibase) provide mature and well-tested technical infrastructure for collaborative knowledge production.

Challenges. The main difficulty of this variant lies in navigation and user experience. Many wiki systems rely on a record-and-property data model that is not specifically tailored to cultural-heritage catalogues. As a result, additional interface design, theming, or explanatory material may be necessary to meet user expectations. Another key challenge concerns quality control: implementing effective review processes and clear attribution mechanisms without discouraging meaningful public participation requires careful governance. There is no universal solution for balancing openness and scholarly reliability.

Examples. [Media contributed to Wikimedia Commons by the Swiss National Library, stained glass in the People's Collection Wales](#)

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Formats for publishing synthesized research

Essays and volumes via publishers. Essays are the traditional publishing format for synthesized research in most humanities disciplines. Whether part of a monograph, an edited volume, or a journal issue, they translate easily into digital publishing formats. Working with a publisher to produce hybrid or digital-only volumes has the advantage of preserving established prestige, which often stems from the publisher's brand, distribution network, and typesetting services. These advantages are preserved when digital publications take the form of a PDF file or, to a lesser extent, an e-book (e.g. EPUB). Even where digital files serve as the primary distribution format, most publishers offer print-on-demand services via their online store fronts.

Challenges. Digital-only publications that follow the print tradition may also take liberties not afforded by print production: continuous journals, for example, can publish articles as soon as they are ready rather than waiting for a complete issue. However, achieving 'the best of both worlds' may require additional effort: a PDF may contain links to catalogue data, but for these references to function in print, stable (and preferably short) identifiers must exist in the catalogue. Careful examination of the publisher's business model is recommended to assess the likely longevity of the publishing contract, the actual openness of open-access agreements, the extent of user tracking, and the beneficiaries of content licences granted to third-parties, such as companies trading in 'AI' training data.

Example. [Lumières nouvelles sur le sacré: Arts verriers du Groupe de Saint-Luc](#)

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<i>Interoperability</i>	Open standard	Proprietary standard	Platform-specific

<i>Funding</i>	Public	Independent	Commercial
<i>Availability</i>	Long-term storage	Project length	Ephemeral content
<i>Curation</i>	Citizen scientists	QA-checked content	Expert authors

Essays and volumes via library repositories. In response to the power-imbalance created by large commercial publishers, an increasing number of library- or scholar-led repositories provide similar services, focusing on monographs, edited volumes, and journals. Established publication and distribution channels usually resemble those encountered when working with commercial publishers. A major advantage, however, is public ownership of the publication without the risk of commercial licences.

Challenges. While publishers typically provide templates, citation styles, and legal support, libraries or scholar-led initiatives often offer less prescriptive guidance. In such cases, applying established typesetting and citation standards is advisable as a mark of scholarly quality and due diligence.

Examples. [Bulletin vol. 39 published via OpenEdition, publishing via arthistoricum.net \(Heidelberg University Library\)](#)

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<i>Interoperability</i>	Open standard	Proprietary standard	Platform-specific
<i>Funding</i>	Public	Independent	Commercial
<i>Availability</i>	Long-term storage	Project length	Ephemeral content
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Blog-like essay and volume publishing. Self-hosted blog software may also provide a suitable infrastructure for publishing short or long texts, including complete volumes. This may include links to research data catalogues and downloadable PDF versions of entries. One example of this format's flexibility is Vidimus, a quarterly online magazine about stained glass published via WordPress. Its content ranges from short items, such as news, conservation updates, obituaries, and details of lectures and conferences, to more substantial contributions, including (formerly) a 'Panel of the Month' authored by an art historian, in-depth features, and (more recently) book reviews.

Challenges. Using blog software instead of publisher or library repositories to publish synthesized research enables the publication of 'web-native' content and offers greater autonomy/control. However, it also places responsibility for long-term preservation on the provider. Plugins can extend platforms such as WordPress into publishing systems, but such solutions may be technically fragile and require continued maintenance. Layout or software

changes may necessitate revisions to previously published content. Although data migration between blog systems is often possible, it typically requires additional technical effort.

Examples. [Recherche sur le vitrail](#), [Stained Glass in Wales blog](#), [Vidimus](#), [Scheibenweise](#)

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<i>Curation</i>	Citizen scientists	QA-checked content	Expert authors

Retrodigitized volumes via library repositories. Putting retrodigitized print volumes online improves accessibility, particularly in an international research context such as the Corpus Vitrearum, where digital access can mitigate travel constraints and facilitate the use of machine-translation services. Many libraries have established scanning and OCR workflows and offer hosting services. Heidelberg University Library, for example, enables national CV committees to make volumes available as PDF and via IIF for a modest fee. The service includes a DOI, page-level linking, and optional annotation functionality.¹⁴

Challenges. Library OCR workflows generally enable text highlighting and copying. However, OCR does not fully reconstruct structural features such as line breaks or hyphenation in the way a structured digital edition would, which may limit search functionality. The main challenge remains rights clearance with publishers, authors, and image-rights holders. The original publishing contract may be a key part of this process: depending on its contents (and the national legal framework), a publisher may, for example, accept retrodigitization before copyright expiration, claim ownership of the typeset version, or claim exclusive publishing rights to a volume.

Example. [Corpus Vitrearum at Heidelberg University Library](#)

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¹⁴ Other libraries may offer equally good service, and the Corpus Vitrearum encourages diverse publication efforts in accordance with national funding frameworks. Beware, however, of libraries using external service providers like Google Books: these services tend to gatekeep what users can do with retrodigitized volumes while granting themselves any re-use licence they need.

<i>Funding</i>	Public	Independent	Commercial
<i>Availability</i>	Long-term storage	Project length	Ephemeral content
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Self-made retrodigitized volumes. It is also possible to produce reasonably good retrodigitized volumes using consumer-grade scanners and OCR software. Such workflows typically generate searchable PDF files, and any PDF version improves access to difficult-to-find or out-of-print material.

Challenges. Compared with professional library-scanned volumes, self-produced retrodigitization projects may be limited by scan quality. While library repositories can host resulting PDFs, robust IIF support requires additional technical work. Rights clearance is equally complex whether digitization is performed independently or by a library.

Example. [Archive of occasional papers and newsletters](#)

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Audio and video essays. Audio and video essays play an increasingly important role in scientific communication since they may reach younger audiences accustomed to bite-sized media. Audio essays are often produced as radio programmes or podcasts, while video essays are typically designed for individual consumption within social-media environments. Both formats allow for less formal communication than written texts. For GLAM institutions in particular, video essays are advantageous, because they avoid the visual–textual divide when discussing artworks.¹⁵

Challenges. The production of audio and video essays requires professional skills comparable to those required for traditional academic publications. The key challenge is to avoid cognitive overload: successful formats break complex academic knowledge into manageable segments and present them within a coherent narrative structure.

Examples. [Art Talk by Vitromusée Romont](#), [Städel museum on its Rineke Dijkstra exhibition](#), [video tutorials of the Decoding Ceramics project](#)

¹⁵ For accessibility reasons, however, it is common practice to also produce a transcript or even subtitles of the recording.

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Formats for publishing digital experiences

Data stories. Some publishing formats blur the distinction between research data and synthesized research by integrating both. One such format is the data story, which combines linear narrative text (similar to a regular essay), with interactive visualizations. Users are encouraged to explore charts, tables, images, or other media, while the surrounding text provides context. Data stories emphasize how knowledge is gained from primary research data. The format resembles electronic lab notebooks (ELNs) in the natural sciences, but has also been adopted as an educational tool in journalism and GLAM contexts.¹⁶

Challenges. Data stories work well alongside repositories and can guide users through large datasets that include images and object metadata. They can address audiences ranging from the broad public, in the case of virtual exhibitions, to specialized research communities. However, not all content lends itself to a data-centric narrative, especially when secondary literature plays a dominant role. Furthermore, there is no widely adopted standard or community format for making data stories available, and interactive elements may not age well. Producing a static archival version is therefore recommended.

Examples. [Städel museum on its Holbein exhibition](#), [Heiter bis wolkig at DDB](#)

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<i>Funding</i>	Public	Independent	Commercial
<i>Availability</i>	Long-term storage	Project length	Ephemeral content
<i>Curation</i>	Citizen scientists	QA-checked content	Expert authors

¹⁶ Story maps are also data stories, but with a focus on maps and geodata.

Digital twins. One of the most recent publication formats, and one that is still loosely defined, is the so-called digital twin. It typically focuses on a single artwork, building, or network of real-world entities (e.g. stained-glass practitioners or workshops). Although digital twins often include a central visualization, this need not be a 3D model. The defining feature is the aggregation of extensive data within a high-performance information system that enables simulation and analyses based on the digital representation rather than the original object. In cultural heritage, applications range from environmental monitoring and damage prevention to, for example, simulating sightlines, integrating restoration data, or linking secondary texts to primary ones.

Challenges. The main challenge lies in defining the purpose and added value of a digital twin. While 3D representations, for example, may be useful, they are not always necessary to answer research questions. Integrating interdisciplinary data requires significant conceptual and technical coordination. Although digital twins attract funding interest, clearer best practices and demonstrable advantages over more established publishing formats, such as knowledge graphs (cf. “Linked Open Data” below), remain necessary.

Examples. [Aioli](#), [Heritalise](#), [Artemis](#)

<i>Audience</i>	Broad public	Domain-specific	Experts
<i>Tradition</i>	Hypertext	Hybrid	Print(-like)
<i>Research data</i>	Repository	Included/linked	None
<i>Searchability</i>	Text and media	Mostly images	Mostly text
<i>Interoperability</i>	Open standard	Proprietary standard	Platform-specific
<i>Funding</i>	Public	Independent	Commercial
<i>Availability</i>	Long-term storage	Project length	Ephemeral content
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Further technological background

Collaboration. Digital publications are often the result of digital-research workflows involving contributors with diverse expertise and locations. Collaboration tools facilitate synchronized editing, annotation, and review processes. Shared documents, datasets, or sources, are typically stored online with controlled-access permissions for multiple contributors and version tracking. In stained-glass research and restoration, such tools support inventory creation (tabular databases), text production (word processors), bibliography management (citation software), and metadata annotation.

Digitization. Common digitization workflows in stained-glass research include high-quality object photography, detailed metadata creation, and spatial documentation using identifiers, maps, or photogrammetry. Partial automation of image and metadata processing is possible, but machine-learning-based pipelines (ML) require clear provenance tracking to enable post-editing and quality-assurance workflows. Since modern cameras and

smartphones frequently apply ML-based enhancements, care must be taken to prevent distortions of colour, texture, and form. The ML settings must be turned off if they damage photographic evidence by distorting colours, adding levels of detail, or altering, for example, facial features to conform to a specific beauty standard. Where ML-enhanced imagery is unavoidable, as in photogrammetry or user-contributed content, clear machine-readable labels are essential to preserve trust in the digital surrogate.

Portals. 'Portal' commonly refers to the software used to provide access to research data, synthesized-research publications, and other digital experiences. Portals determine presentation, interaction, and available formats. While many software solutions rely on relational databases, they should ideally also provide graph-based Linked Open Data (LOD) or machine-actionable APIs. Data sovereignty is a key criterion: even when using third-party repositories, projects should favour open-source, self-hostable solutions that support common data serializations to ensure long-term sustainability. In this way, data (or even entire services) may be rescued in cases where funding runs out, disaster strikes, or political agendas change.

Linked Open Data (LOD). Five-star LOD, associated with the so-called Semantic Web, promotes frictionless reuse by humans and bots. Key criteria include open licences, structured and non-proprietary data formats, persistent identifiers (URIs), alignment with authority files and ontologies, and the use of at least one RDF dialect (Resource Description Framework). Recent versions of IIIF, for example, follow these principles, enabling interoperable viewers independent of hosting platforms. Controlled vocabularies in SKOS (Simple Knowledge Organization System) and metadata standards such as XMP (Extensible Metadata Platform) similarly support cross-platform interoperability. Large collections of RDF (or other graph) data on real-world entities are also known as Knowledge Graphs. Although SPARQL endpoints as publicly accessible graph databases offer powerful federated querying capabilities, they remain underused.

Machine Learning (ML). While algorithms operate deterministically based on fixed rules, ML models generate probabilistic predictions based on patterns learned from training data. Often labelled 'artificial intelligence' (due to their application in the research domain of the same name – not because they are actually artificial or intelligent), ML offers opportunities for automated digitization, improved searching, automated pre-annotation, and exploratory data analyses, just to name a few. However, large language models (LLMs, or 'generative AI') in particular should be used only when they provide clear advantages over conventional algorithms. They are computationally expensive, environmentally costly, and may compromise data sovereignty through dependence on centralized infrastructures. Furthermore, they can reproduce and even enhance biases in training data, rely on copyrighted materials without clear consent, and potentially contribute to the deskilling of specialist expertise.

Further reading

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